

Kinetics of oxidation of methionine by tetramethylammonium fluorochromate in aquo-organic medium – Separation of solvent effect into contributions to initial and transition states

M. Balakrishnan^a, Shahriare Ghammami^b and K. P. Elango^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Gandhigram Rural Institute (Deemed University), Gandhigram-624 302, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : drkpelango@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-0451-2454466

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Imam Khomeini International University, Ghazvin, Iran

Manuscript received 20 June 2005, revised 21 December 2005, accepted 21 February 2006

Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of methionine by tetramethylammonium fluorochromate has been studied under pseudo-first order conditions in aqueous acetic acid mixtures of varying compositions. The rate data is correlated with different solvent parameters using linear multiple regression analysis. From the results, information on the solvent-reactants and the solvent-transition state interactions is obtained.

Keywords : Solvent effect, kinetics, methionine.

A survey of literature shows that the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of methionine by various oxidants is well understood¹⁻⁶. However, no report was made with recently reported⁷ tetramethylammonium fluorochromate (TMAFC) as oxidant. Further, kinetic investigations of redox reactions in aqueous organic solvents and correlation of the reaction rates with various solvent parameters would provide important information regarding the mechanism of such reactions. The objective of the present work, therefore, is to study the title reaction in aqueous acetic acid mixtures of varying compositions, to check the utility of such solvent variation studies in the interpretation of mechanism and, in particular, to separate the effect of solvent on the title reaction into contributions to initial and transition states.

Results and discussion

The experimental results of the kinetics of oxidation of methionine by TMAFC in water are given in Table 1.

The reactions are first order with respect to TMAFC and TsOH. The reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in the concentration of Met (Table 1). A plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{Met}]$ is linear with a positive intercept on the rate axis indicating that the reaction follows Michealis-Menten type mechanism. The decrease in rate with added Mn^{II} indicates TMAFC behaves as a two-electron oxi-

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of methionine by TMAFC in water at 25 ± 0.2 °C

10^2 [Met] (mol dm ³)	10^3 [TMAFC] (mol dm ³)	10^2 [Acid] (mol dm ³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	1.00	4.0	5.91
1.5	1.00	4.0	10.24
2.0	1.00	4.0	11.58
2.5	1.00	4.0	12.16
3.0	1.00	4.0	14.18
1.0	1.00	4.0	3.25 ^a
1.0	1.00	4.0	5.91
1.0	1.25	4.0	5.95
1.0	1.50	4.0	5.88
1.0	1.75	4.0	5.93
1.0	2.00	4.0	5.92
1.0	1.00	1.0	1.10
1.0	1.00	2.0	2.83
1.0	1.00	3.0	4.33
1.0	1.00	4.0	5.91
1.0	1.00	5.0	10.99

^acontained 5×10^{-4} M Mn^{II} .

dant¹. This observation is further supported by the fact that the oxidation of methionine by TMAFC failed to

induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile and thus the formation of free radicals is unlikely in this reaction.

The rate constants (k_{obs}) for the oxidation of methionine at 25, 30 and 35 °C ($[\text{Met}]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{TMAFC}]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\text{H}^+]_0 = 3 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) are 4.33×10^{-4} , 5.35×10^{-4} and $7.71 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. The activation parameters were calculated as: $\Delta H^\ddagger = 45.25 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -158.56 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $\Delta G^\ddagger = 92.66 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

The observed pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}), for different mole fractions of the added organic co-solvent, are collected in Table 2.

Table 2. Pseudo-first order rate constants for the oxidation of methionine by TMAFC in aqueous acetic acid mixtures at $25 \pm 0.2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

<i>m.f.</i> of	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
AcOH	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$	0.09	2.63	5.32	6.89	17.43	42.06	48.21	120.45

$[\text{Met}] = 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{TMAFC}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}^+] = 7.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The influence of relative permittivity (ϵ_r) of the medium on the rate was analyzed using Laidler and Eyring equation⁸. A plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/\epsilon_r$ is nonlinear (Fig. 1) with an explained variance of only 71%. Similarly a plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus the Reichardt's⁹ solvent parameter E_T (30) is satisfactory with an explained variance of 95%. These statistical results indicate that no

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus inverse of relative permittivity of the medium for the oxidation of methionine by TMAFC.

single solvent parameter could possibly account for the multitude of solute-solvent interactions on the molecular microscopic level.

In order to obtain a deeper insight into the specific and non-specific solvent-solvent-solute interactions, which influence the reactivity, we have tried to adopt the solvatochromic comparison method developed by Kamlet and Taft¹⁰. This method may be used to unravel, quantify, correlate and rationalize multiple interacting solvent effects on reactivity. The kinetic data were correlated with the solvatochromic parameters α , β and π^* characteristic of the different mixtures in the form of Linear Solvation Energy Relationship.

$$\log k = A_0 + s\pi^* + a\alpha + b\beta$$

where π^* is an index of solvent dipolarity/polarizability which measures the ability of the solvent to stabilise a charge or a dipole by virtue of its dielectric effect, α is the solvent HBD (hydrogen bond donor) acidity, β is the solvent HBA (hydrogen bond acceptor) basicity of the solvent in a solute to solvent hydrogen bond and A_0 is the regression value of the solute property in the reference solvent cyclohexane. The regression coefficients s , a and b measure the relative susceptibilities of the solvent dependent solute property $\log k$ to the indicated solvent parameter. The solvatochromic parameters employed in the present study were from literature¹¹. The rates of oxidation for both the compounds studied show excellent correlations with solvent via the above LSER. The values in the parentheses are the standard errors.

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} = -27.2 (\pm 11.5) - 6.4 (\pm 0.6) \pi^* + 12.6 (\pm 6.0) \alpha + 30.9 (\pm 8.9) \beta$$

$(R^2 = 0.982, sd = 0.17, P_{\pi^*} = 13, P_{\alpha} = 25 \text{ and } P_{\beta} = 62)$

The results of the correlation analysis indicate that the specific solute-solvent-solvent interactions play a major role in governing the reactivity as indicated by the percentage contributions of HBA and HBD terms. The positive sign of the coefficients of these terms indicate that the transition state solvation, through hydrogen bonding, by the solvent mixture is extensive than the reactants. The rate of the reaction is influenced, to a very lesser extent, by solvent dipolarity/polarizability. The negative sign of this coefficient suggest that the reactants are extensively solvated, through non-specific interactions, by the solvent mixture than the transition state.

On the basis of thermodynamic properties, particularly molar excess functions X^E , water-acetic acid mix-

ture has been classified as a typical non-aqueous positive (TNAP) mixture, for which G^E is positive. Further, an extra thermodynamic analysis indicates that, at least qualitatively, if G^E is positive the solute should be more soluble in the mixture than predicted from the solubilities in two pure solvents¹². The increase in rate of oxidation with increase in mole fraction of acetic acid in the mixture may be due to the fact that the transition state is more hydrophobic than the initial state, so that the added TNAP co-solvent stabilizes it.

To conclude, specific solute-solvent-solvent interactions play a major role in governing the reactivity while the non-specific long range interactions play very little role. With increase in mole fraction of organic co-solvent in the mixture, the transition state is stabilized to a larger extent compared to the reactants consequently increase in rate of oxidation. Based on the kinetic observations it is proposed that in the first step TMAFC gets protonated, the protonated oxidant attacks the substrate to form a Michaelis-Menten type complex in a pre-equilibrium step and which consequently decomposes to give the product in a slow step. The proposed scheme envisages an oxygen atom transfer from the oxidant. The electrophilic attack on the sulphide sulphur can be viewed as an S_N2 reaction. An S_N2 transition state (more hydrophobic) is supported by the observed solvent effect.

Experimental

Tetramethylammonium fluorochromate (TMAFC) was prepared by reported method⁷ and its purity was checked by iodometric method. Reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping an excess of the substrate over the oxidant. The progress of the reactions was followed by estimating the unreacted oxidant iodometrically at 25 ± 0.2 °C. The rate constants (k_{obs}) were determined by least squares method, from the linear plots of $\log [TMAFC]$ versus time. Replicate runs showed

that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The stoichiometry and product analysis were carried out as reported earlier^{1,2}. Correlation analyses were carried out using Microcal Origin (version 3.5) computer software. The goodness of the fit was discussed using correlation coefficient (r), standard deviation (sd) and coefficient of multiple determination (R^2). The percentage contribution (P_x) of a parameter to the total effect on reactivity was computed using the regression coefficient of each parameter as reported earlier¹³.

References

1. M. Pandeeswaran, Bincy John, D. S. Bhuvaneshwari and K. P. Elango, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **70**, 145.
2. A. Goyal and S. Kothari, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2003, **42**, 2129.
3. V. Sharma, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 418.
4. V. Sharma, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 607.
5. R. Srinivasan, C. V. Ramesh. W. Madhulatha and K. Balasubramanian, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1996, **35**, 480
6. D. S. Bhuvaneshwari, B. John, M. Pandeeswaran and K. P. Elango, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* in press.
7. A. R. Mahjoub, S. Ghammami and M. Z. Kassae, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 4555.
8. E. S. Amis and J. F. Hinton, "Solvent Effect of Chemical Phenomena", Vol. 1, Academic Press, New York, 1973.
9. C. Reichardt, "Solvents and Solvent Effects in Organic Chemistry", VCH, Weinheim, 1988.
10. M. J. Kamlet, J. M. Abboud, M. H. Abraham and R. W. Taft, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, **48**, 2877.
11. Y. Marcus, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1994, 1751.
12. M. J. Blandamer and J. Burgess, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1975, **4**, 55.
13. J. Shorter, "Correlation Analysis of Organic Reactivity", Research Studies Press, Letchworth, 1982.